

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH TO ASSESS THE
EDUCATIONAL PERCEPTION OF THE MEDICAL STUDENTS
THROUGH DREEM QUESTIONNAIRE**¹Dr. Syed Mohsin Ali, ²Dr. Asma Majid, ³Dr. Ayesha Muneer¹School of Public Health, Shandong University, Jinan, China²WMO, THQ Hospital Gojra³Punjab Medical College, Faisalabad**Abstract:**

Objective: Chief feat of any educational environment rely on the advantages provided to the learners and this act as supplementary to the process of learning. DREEM serves as a measuring instrument to measure learning environment performance. We intended in this study to examine the medical student's perception about educational environment in preclinical years; moreover, the objective of the study was to relate and contrast the scores of Dundee Ready Educational Environment Measure (DREEM) with previously available literature. **Methodology:** We gave the DREEM questionnaire to three hundred students of Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from June 2016 to February 2017. **Results:** Out of three hundred (300), two hundred and eighty-six (286) students completed the DREEM questionnaire. After analysis of the data mean score was $M=113.68$. Mean of students' perception of teachers was (26.63 ± 10.177) and mean of students' perception about the learning was (26.65 ± 10.235) . Conversely, the mean for students' atmosphere perception, social self-perception, and academic self-perception were (26.89 ± 10.89) , (16.34 ± 6.70) and (17.17 ± 6.73) respectively. **Conclusion:** Even though (DREEM) scores displayed some improvement from available scores of that medical college. The result also emphasized the zones which still require enhancement.

Keywords: Dundee Ready Educational Environment Measure (DREEM), Medical Students and Educational Environment.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Syed Mohsin Ali,
School of Public Health, Shandong University,
Jinan, China

QR code

Please cite this article in press Syed Mohsin Ali et al., *A Cross-Sectional Research to Assess the Educational Perception of the Medical Students through Dreem Questionnaire.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

The educational environment is defined as the helpful method that facilitates the learner, which may include the setup and physical situations; nature of the leadership and instructive methodology; social setting and the nature of patient consideration [1]. The view of students with respect to the educational environment impacts their academic growth and behaviour [2, 3]. An inspiring educational environment cultivates profound learning among students, makes it less demanding to accomplish learning outcomes and in the long run prompts great medical practice by doctors [4, 5].

Even though numerous tools exist to measure such as (DREEM). International Delphi Panel of Professional Health Educationists created this highly recognized tool to measure the perception of undergraduates about the educational environment in health professions. Moreover, it also highlights the drawbacks of medical institutions which helps to modify the educational strategy [6 – 8]. The objective of the present study was to measure the environment of the education among basic science students by utilizing (DREEM). Muhammad Shahzad et al. conducted this study in the same institute which displayed low scores [9]. From then on, the inclusion of new building, making a section of medical education, procuring skilled staff, and modification of learning environment according to the student's needs. This study features students' perception to the progressions made in a framework, educational programs and staff improvement. These findings permit further research in improvement and advancement of the educational environment.

METHODOLOGY:

A cross-sectional survey design was used. We gave the DREEM questionnaire to three hundred students

Table – I: SPoL: We measured this it putting forth twelve questions and no question had scored less than two

Questions About	Mean	±SD
Class participation is encouraged	2.060	0.802
Teaching is stimulating	2.210	0.872
Interactive Teaching	2.300	0.906
Competence Development	2.180	0.838
Focused Teaching	2.220	0.853
Confidence Development	2.190	0.918
Good use of Teaching	2.100	0.754
Over-emphasizes factual learning	2.410	0.835
Clarity about Learning Objectives	2.330	0.827
Encouragement through Teaching	2.120	0.917
Long Term Learning	2.020	0.839
Teacher Centered Teaching	2.510	0.874

of Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from June 2016 to February 2017. Students from 1st & 2nd-year MBBS and Basic Science Sections were involved in this study. Non-probability and convenient samples were used for this purpose. Students of clinical classes and BDS were not included in this research. DREEM was applied to three hundred (300) students. Before the application of the questionnaire and also shared the research purpose with students. Students are asked to do not show their identity. The consent form was signed a form each participant of the study. Data were obtained from two hundred and eighty-six students (286) as fourteen (14) students were unable to give back the form. DREEM inquiry form consists of fifty question of various subsets as mentioned in the given tabular data [10].

DREEM data inquiry form provides info about 5 subset's score, total score, and score of each question. The score in every subset had been partitioned into four quarters of 25 % each. Questionnaire items with ≥ 3.5 mean scores were taken as real positive, while a mean score under 2 recommended a need to alteration. Data was analyzed on SPSS and mean score was obtained. Moreover, each item of the questionnaire were also calculated and examined.

RESULTS:

In sum of 300, 286 students completed questionnaire. Response rate was 95.34 percent and total score was 113.68 / 200 with 56.84%. The results disclosed that student's perception of teachers was 26.63 / 44 (60.52 %), perception about learning was 26.65 / 48 (55.52 %), students' social self-perception was 16.34 / 28 (58.35 %), perception of atmosphere was 26.89 / 48 (56 %), academic self-perception was 17.17 / 32 (53.65 %).

Table – II: SPoT: We measured this it putting forth eleven questions having forty-four as a total score. Students didn't observe any surprising quality in teachers as no question had a score greater than or equal to (3.5). There was a reverse order in a score of items no 08, 09 and 50 as well as they were negative.

Questions About	Mean	±SD
Knowledgeable Teachers	2.010	0.759
Teachers Patience	2.320	0.948
Teacher's Ridiculing Behaviour	2.820	0.945
Authoritative Attitude of Teachers	2.160	0.778
Better Communication Skills	2.590	1.582
Better Feedback Facilities	2.400	0.796
Constructive Criticism	2.690	0.836
Clear Examples	2.170	0.816
Angry Teachers	2.730	0.934
Class Preparation	2.040	0.770
Student's Irritating Attitude	2.700	1.013

Table – III: SASP: We measured it by putting forth 08 questions having thirty-two as a total score. The three items

10, 31 and 45 had mean scores as 1.50, 1.90 and 1.97 respectively (less than two) which depicted the system's serious faults.

Questions About	Mean	±SD
Learning Strategies	2.300	0.941
Confident About Passing	1.500	0.719
Preparedness for Profession	2.320	0.883
Good Last Year Work	2.090	0.860
All required data is Memorized	2.550	0.919
Learning about Empathy	1.910	0.764
Well-developed Problem-Solving Skills	2.460	0.866
Relevant Learning Experience	1.970	0.782

Table – IV: SPoA: We measured it by putting forth 12 questions having forty-eight as a total score. The score in all of the twelve items was between two and three, whereas, only item 17 and item 35 were negative.

Questions About	Mean	±SD
Relax Environment	2.210	0.829
Good Time-Table	2.220	0.934
Cheating is a Serious Issue	2.490	0.994
Relax Environment Lectures	2.010	0.843
Development Opportunities	2.360	0.841
Social Comfort	2.100	0.736
Friendly Seminars	2.170	0.964
Disappointing Experience	2.190	0.986
Better Concentration	2.350	0.936
Better Enjoyment Facilities	2.280	1.052
Motivating Environment for Learning	2.140	0.824
Liberty to Ask Questions	2.370	0.956

Table – V: SSSP: We measured it by putting forth 07 questions having twenty-eight as a total score. The score less than two was only item 19. Item 3 had mean score maximum of all i.e. 2.89.

Questions About	Mean	±SD
Better Supportive System for Stressed	2.890	0.937
Too tiresome to Enjoy	2.340	0.951
Rarely Bored	2.530	0.979
Better Peer Group	2.010	0.979
Good Social Life	1.930	0.796
Lonely Feeling	2.300	1.057
Pleasant Accommodation	2.340	1.008

DISCUSSION:

If student learns and practice good things and achieve

their learning outcomes then it means it is the positive perception of the educational environment

[11, 12]. There are many factors which affect the perception of medical students like economic, social, cultural, experience [12]. DREEM owing to its reliability and validity is well accepted among such tools which measure educational environment [13, 15]. In interpretation, Ruffin and McAleer observed that there are several problems for the score from 51 to 100 [16].

In the present research, the students display a mean score of positive perception as 113.68 / 200. In previous research conducted on the previous year's students by Shahzad et., the mean score was 90.4 / 200 [9]. This improved score is owing to much-improved infrastructure and accessibility of skilled staff.

Overall mean score differs a lot as soon as we relate it with other internationally and nationally organized studies. For instance, in Malaysia, two studies show much difference when having a mean (125 / 200) and other with a mean (133 / 200) and (134 / 200) [18, 23]. Studies in Sri Lanka, Trinidad and India reported low mean scores as (108 / 200) [17], (109 / 200) [25] and (114 / 200 & 107 / 200) [19, 25] respectively. The least score was in King Saud University (89 / 200) [21]. In UK high scores were as, (139 / 200) [22] & (144 / 200) [24]; whereas, in Nepal high scores were as, 130 / 200 [3]. Higher scores show that medical institution has a positive educational environment which they attained by hard work in providing a class environment as well as by utilizing students centred teaching methodology.

In the present research students perceived student-centered teaching as (26.63 / 44), better social self-perception as (16.34 / 28), positive learning approach (26.65 / 48), a positive atmosphere as (26.89 / 48) and good educational self-perception as (17.17 / 32). In this research, 04 questions of DREEM were having score 02 or less. These questions are of social perception and student's academic subscales. Low scores show student's perception about the higher rate of failure, deficiency of community life and deficiency of teaching empathy. It is highly recommended that the curriculum must focus on empathy, self-perception, and community-centered activities. Faculty must provide students with better role models and encourage for self-learning in learning centres like library [4].

Mean scores of all items were positive with least score of 2.02 on response 47 and a highest score of 2.51 on response 48. These figures show that teaching is more students centred than teachers

centred. Teachers are kind, have the well subject knowledge, prepared and have good skills in communication as indicated by students' perception of teachers (SPoT). negative scores such as students and teachers' attitude should get improvement.

In this study, we focused on and compared the perception of private medical college's student with the already published scores. Score have shifted from 21.80 [9] to 26.65 in Students' perception of learning (SPoL), from 20.40 [9] to 26.63 in Students' perception of teachers (SPoT), from 13.50 [9] to 17.70 in Students' academic self-perception (SASP), from 22.60 [9] to 26.89 in Students' perception of atmosphere (SPoA) and from 12.30 [9] to 16.34 in Students' social self-perception (SSSP) with having adjustment in infrastructure, creation of separate medical education department as well as induction of skilled teaching staff. Future researches should be large enough to quantify the perceptions of the students in public sectors as well as private sector medical colleges. Not only this but also the authorities should focus on the curriculum's affective domain.

CONCLUSION:

Though DREEM scores displayed enhancement from earlier available scores of that medical college, it also emphasized the zones requiring additional development.

REFERENCES:

1. Mayya S, Roff S. Students' perceptions of the educational environment: a comparison of academic achievers and under-achievers at Kasturba Medical College, India. *Educ Health (Abingdon)*. 2004 Nov 1; 17(3):280–91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13576280400002445>
2. Al-Ayed IH, Sheik SA. Assessment of the educational environment at the College of Medicine of King Saud University, Riyadh. *East Mediterr Health J*. 2008; 14(4):953–9.
3. Varma R, Tiyagi E, Gupta JK. Determining the quality of educational climate across multiple undergraduate teaching sites using the DREEM inventory. *BMC Med Educ*. 2005 Feb 21; 5(1):8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6920-5-8>
4. Zamzuri AT, Ali AN, Roff S, Mc Aleer S. Students' perceptions of the educational environment at dental training college. *Malays Dent J*. 2004; 25:15–26.
5. Miles S, Leinster SJ. Comparing staff and student perceptions of the student experience at a new medical school. *Med Teach*. 2009 Jan 1; 31(6):539–

46. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01421590802139732>
6. Bassaw B, Roff S, McAleer S, Roopnarine Singh S, De Lisle J, Teeluck Singh S, et al. Students' perspectives on the educational environment, Faculty of Medical Sciences, Trinidad. *Med Teach* 2003 Jan 1; 25(5): 522-6. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0142159031000137409>
 7. Divaris K, Barlow PJ, Chendea SA, Cheong WS, Dounis A, Dragan IF, et al. The academic environment: the students' perspective. *Eur J Dent Educ*. 2008 Feb 1; 12(s1):120-30. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0579.2007.00494.x>
 8. Miles S, Leinster SJ. Medical students' perceptions of their educational environment: expected versus actual perceptions. *Med Educ*. 2007 Mar 1; 41(3):265-72. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2929.2007.02686.x>
 9. Khan JS, Tabasum S, Yousafzai UK, Fatima M. DREEM ON: Validation of the Dundee Ready Education Environment Measure in Pakistan. *J Pak Med Assoc*. 2011 Sep 1; 61(9):885.
 10. Anwar MS, Anwar I, Ghafoor T. Medical students' perceptions of the educational environment in remote and urban area medical colleges. *AHPE* 2015 Jan 1;1(1).
 11. Hammond SM, O'Rourke M, Kelly M, Bennett D, O'Flynn SA. A psychometric appraisal of the DREEM. *BMC Med Educ*. 2012 Jan 12; 12:2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6920-12-2>
 12. Jamieson S. Likert scales: how to (ab)use them. *Med Educ*. 2004 Dec 1; 38(12):1217-8. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2929.2004.02012.x>
 13. Sobral DT. Medical students' self-appraisal of first-year learning outcomes: use of the course valuing inventory. *Med Teach*. 2004 May 1; 26(3):234-8. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0142159042000192028>
 14. Al-Naggar RA, Abdulghani M, Osman MT, Al-Kubaisy W, Daher AM, Nor Aripin KN, et al. The Malaysia DREEM: perceptions of medical students about the learning environment in a medical school in Malaysia. *Adv Med Educ Pract*. 2014; 5:177-84.
 15. Al-Kabbaa AF, Ahmad HH, Saeed AA, Abdalla AM, Mustafa AA. Perception of the learning environment by students in a new medical school in Saudi Arabia: Areas of concern. *J Taibah Uni Med Sc*. 2012 Dec 31; 7(2):69-75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtumed.2012.11.001>
 16. Mahrous M, Al-Shorman H, Ahmad MS. Assessment of the educational environment in a newly established dental college. *J Educ Ethics Dent*. 2013 Jan 1; 3(1):6. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0974-7761.126935>
 17. McAleer S, Roff S. A practical guide to using the Dundee Ready Education Environment Measure (DREEM). *AMEE Medical education guide*.2001; 23:29-33.
 18. Jeffrey MT, McAleer S, Fernando S, Marasinghe RB. Using the DREEM questionnaire to gather baseline information on an evolving medical school in Sri Lanka. *Med Teach*. 2005; 27(4):348-52. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01421590500151005>
 19. Hassan II. A Study of Stressors and Coping Strategies Among First Year Nursing Students in the College of Polytech Mara, Kota Bharu, Kelantan [master's thesis] Kota Bharu (Kelantan): University Sains Malaysia; 2007.
 20. Abraham R, Ramnarayan K, Vinod P, Torke S. Students' perceptions of learning environment in an Indian medical school. *BMC Med Educ*. 2008; 8:20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6920-8-20>
 21. Roff S, McAleer S. What is educational climate? *Med Teach*. 2001 Jul; 23(4):333-4. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01421590120063312>
 22. Dornan T, Bundy C. What can experience add to early medical education? Consensus survey. *BMJ*. 2004 Oct 7; 329(7470): 834. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.329.7470.834>
 23. Roff S, McAleer S, Ifere OS, Bhattacharya S. A global diagnostic tool for measuring educational environment: comparing Nigeria and Nepal. *Med Teach*. 2001 Jan 1; 23(4): 378-82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01421590120043080>
 24. Maudsley RF. Role models and the learning environment: Essential elements in effective medical education. *Acad Med* 2001 May 1; 76(5): 432-4. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00001888-200105000-00011>
 25. Whittle SR, Whelan B, Murdoch-Eaton DG. DREEM and beyond: studies of the educational environment as a means for its enhancement. *Educ Health*. 2007 May 1; 20(1):7.